

“I have some serious doubts about this vaccine...” – Generic conspiracy beliefs affect the acceptance of the Covid-19 vaccination

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Author Contribution Statement

HB conceptualized the study, created the material, conducted the study, analysed the data, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript (80%). SW helped conceptualizing the study, checked the materials, and proofread the manuscript (20%).

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Open Science and Ethics Statement

The Ethics Committee approved this Study under “GZ. 39/55/63 ex 2020/21”

This study was preregistered here: https://osf.io/8stm9/?view_only=a5079a04a43640459ee6293c767cde30

All data and materials can be found here: https://osf.io/dp3hz/?view_only=ff2fd94a70134adaba2eef26b416c06b

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Abstract

The start of the Covid-19 vaccine rollout in early 2021 was accompanied by miscommunication from medical and political actors and decision-makers with regard to its availability. In central European countries, it was not clear when and to what extent vaccines would be available to the public. As a working hypothesis, we assumed that this vagueness in media communication might affect the vaccination acceptance in conspiracy believers, who are otherwise assumed to have a low acceptance of vaccination. In a large preregistered online study (N = 659) we did not find evidence that media communication affects vaccination acceptance, but conspiracy believers tended to accept the vaccine more if they were given the option to choose their preferred vaccine. This latter exploratory finding could be confirmed in a follow-up study (N = 199).

Keywords: Covid-19, vaccination acceptance, conspiracy beliefs, media information

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Open Science and Ethics Statement

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Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has become a breeding ground for misinformation and conspiracy theories on social media platforms (see e.g., Ahmed et al., 2020; Bruns et al., 2020). Although a spread of conspiracy theories is common during large-scale crisis situations (van Prooijen & Douglas, 2017), believing in these theories may lead to harmful consequences for people: for instance, there is much evidence that believing in Covid-19-related conspiracies theories (e.g., that Bill Gates wants to implant microchips in our bodies via the vaccine) goes hand in hand with hesitance to get vaccinated or to refuse a vaccine all together (e.g., Jennings et al., 2021, Sallam et al., 2021, Ullah et al., 2021, Pummerer et al., 2023).

However, beside these close links between conspiracy belief and behavior, a growing body of studies suggests that more *generic* beliefs in conspiracies (e.g., that powerful people are plotting in politics; see Brotherton et al., 2013;) may be related to anti-vaccine attitudes as well (Salvador Casara et al., 2019; Callaghan et al., 2019; Farhart et al., 2022; Oleksy et al., 2023). Here, we want to investigate this idea – how generic conspiracy beliefs affect vaccination acceptance – in the context of the early Covid-19 vaccine rollout.

The early vaccine rollout offered a unique situation to study general conspiracy beliefs and their effects. As vaccine manufacturers started producing and distributing Covid-19 vaccines in early 2021, medical and political decision makers, as well as media outlets in several European countries did show a temporary discord in their communication. Ambiguities arose from early coordination issues and an insufficient set up of vaccination centres in the cities that caused vaccination delays until early summer (Charisius, 2021; Krutzler & Arora, 2021). More importantly, the European Medicines Agency (2021a) reported about rarely occurring side-effects with one particular vaccine, namely the one from “AstraZeneca”, which seemed to be related to extremely rare cases of blood clots. Although the agency reported that benefits of a vaccination still outweigh its risk (European Medicines Agency, 2021b), this conclusion was not initially shared by the Robert Koch Institute (2021), which further steered uncertainties in the public (Infratest Dimap, 2021, p. 5-6). The media extensively covered these

events (see Figure 1 for a time line of events), and their impact on public vaccination choices – in interplay with prevailing conspiracy beliefs – remained uncertain.

[Figure 1 here]

One could argue that supporters of conspiracy theories generally distrust authorities when it comes to official information conveyed through the mainstream news media and that they might want to uphold a conspiracy narrative when the social-political circumstances are ambiguous. However, it is also conceivable that the vaccine supply delays might have intensified suspicions, catering conspiracy believers' apprehension that influential actors purposely withhold limited vaccines. Specifically, this situation of information ambiguity could lead to the interpretation that a relevant information (i.e., when the vaccine is available) may be suppressed by politicians and medical decision makers. And they do so because they secretly claim the new technology (i.e., the vaccine) for themselves and thereby accept that the public could get harmed in the process.

This scenario is plausible as others have argued for (Brotherton et al., 2013) and partially shown (Petersen et al., 2021) that transparency about negative features of a certain information (e.g., rare side effects of a vaccine) can have negative effects on people's behavior (e.g., vaccination acceptance).¹ Moreover, it would fit conspiracy believers' existential need that they want to *avoid harm* through powerful actors (e.g., in politics), while also addressing believers' epistemic *need to know*, which relevant information is being hidden from them by these actors (Douglas et al., 2017; van Prooijen & Douglas, 2017).

Therefore, we establish the latter reasoning in two working hypotheses, where we account for generic belief in conspiracies, focussing on government-related and wellbeing-related

¹ Although we want to acknowledge that – as a reviewer noted – this suppression of information could also strengthen the belief in a certain conspiracy theory (see Nyhan et al., 2016, Swami et al., 2012).

conspiracies of the people, which are in accordance with our preregistration

(https://osf.io/8stm9/?view_only=a5079a04a43640459ee6293c767cde30):

Hypothesis 1 & Hypothesis 2

Beside a negative main effect of conspiracy belief on vaccination acceptance, participants who strongly believe in government-related (H1) and wellbeing-related conspiracies (H2) should show higher acceptance of vaccination when media information highlights uncertainty of the Covid-19 vaccine compared to when media information highlights availability about the Covid-19 vaccine in the near future.²

Hypothesis 3

Due to the controversy about specific vaccines and their side effects (see above), we also hypothesized that when people experience more agency to choose a vaccine, their acceptance might be positively affected: Participants express a higher acceptance of Covid-19 vaccination when they are offered to choose among available vaccines compared to when no choice is offered.

Exploratory Questions

For means of data exploration, we want to include all additional conspiracy belief measures (see Methods section), as well as political orientation – a common predictor for vaccination hesitation (see Rossen et al., 2019) – in one linear model to see, which independent variable turns out to be most robust predicting vaccination acceptance. Then we want to check, whether the choice effect that we potentially confirm when testing H3, is particularly relevant for conspiracy believers. That is, if we want to investigate, whether the choice effect matters most for people, who score high conspiracy belief. More exploratory questions are addressed in the supplemental materials.

² See hypothesized effect of interest pattern: https://osf.io/4ka5q?view_only=ff2fd94a70134adaba2eef26b416c06b

Methods

We set up an online study (Questback GmbH, 2021), where participants had to give their informed consent, followed by demographic questions on their sex, age, and political orientation.

Then, we showed participants a short (appr. 100 sec) summary video on the media information on the vaccine for Covid-19, which randomly either highlighted that the vaccine availability is *uncertain* due different circumstances (see above) or *available* soon. Importantly, both contents were represented in the news media at the time and we provided links to the original sources.

Next, we collected data on our dependent variables (DVs):

- DV 1: “To what extend would you currently accept a Covid-19 vaccination?” (in German: “Impfbereitschaft”), (0% = “no acceptance”, 50% = “undecided”, 100% = “full acceptance”; in 10% steps)
- DV 2: acceptance to receive a vaccination *if they could choose the vaccine* (0 to 100%).

Finally, we employed measures covering belief in conspiracy theories, namely an adapted version of the generic conspiracy belief scale (GCBS; Brotherton et al., 2013) with focus on government-related conspiracies (for H1; three items, example item: “Some EU governments are involved in the murder of innocent citizens and/or well-known public figures, and keep this a secret”, rating scales from 1 = “definitely not true” to 5 = “definitely true”) and wellbeing-related conspiracies (for H2; three items, example item: “Experiments involving new drugs or technologies are routinely carried out on the public without their knowledge or consent”).

For further data exploration, we collected data on malevolent-global and information-related conspiracies, as well as on single-item belief in conspiracy theory scale by Lantian and

colleagues (2016). We also collected information on their vaccination status and other variables that were not of primary interest.³

Results

We reached 1668 people via social media groups and email distribution of the local university. After applying preregistered exclusion criteria, our final sample contained $N = 659$ ($M_{\text{age}} = 32$ years, $SD = 11$ years, min-max: 18-80; $n_{\text{female}} = 480$, 73%; $n_{\text{lgbtq}} = 1$, ~0.002%; $n_{\text{university degree}} = 320$, 49%), which was in accordance with our a-priori power analysis for $1-\beta > 0.80$, $\alpha = .05$ to spot effects of $d = 0.4$ ($\beta \sim 0.14$). All descriptive statistics and inter-item correlations for all variables of interest can be found in Table 1.

[Table 1 here]

Confirmatory Analysis

We tested H1 and 2 (i.e., the interaction of conspiracy beliefs and video information) in two 3 (conspiracy belief: low tercile, medium tercile and high tercile) \times 2 (video information: vaccine available vs. uncertain) ANOVAs. We found two large negative main effects of conspiracy belief on vaccination acceptance (IV government conspiracy: $F(2, 654) = 42.61$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.12$; IV wellbeing conspiracy: $F(2, 654) = 142.75$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.30$), but no main effects of the video information ($ps \geq .316$, $\eta_p^2s \leq 0.002$), and – contrary to our hypotheses – no interaction effects ($ps \geq .587$, $\eta_p^2s \leq 0.002$). As one can see in Figures 2A and B, we also confirmed the main effects when treating conspiracy beliefs as continuous predictors (IV government conspiracy: $t(656) = 9.78$, $p < .001$, $b = -14.09$, 95% $CI [-16.91, 11.26]$, $\beta = -0.36$; IV wellbeing conspiracy: $t(656) = 19.39$, $p < .001$, $b = -23.06$, 95% $CI [-25.09, 19.39]$, $\beta = -0.60$).

³ All further information on variables and materials can be found on the OSF:

https://osf.io/6v47d/?view_only=ff2fd94a70134adaba2eef26b416c06b and

https://osf.io/nceyb/?view_only=ff2fd94a70134adaba2eef26b416c06b

As we collected data on participants vaccination status, we found that $n = 386$ (58.57%) indicated that they were already registered for or already received the vaccine. Therefore, we rerun the previous analyses with the remaining sample of $n = 273$. Still, the only effects we found were two main effects for government ($F(2, 267) = 21.95, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.14$) and wellbeing-related conspiracies ($F(2, 267) = 60.08, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .31$), confirming the previous analysis (see supporting information in the supplemental materials, Table S3 to S5).

Testing H3 with a paired-samples t test, we compared the acceptance of vaccination ($M=72.39\%$, $SE=1.48$) with the acceptance of vaccination when one could choose the vaccine ($M=79.10\%$, $SE = 1.36$). We found a mean difference in the hypothesized direction, $b=6.70$, 95% CI [5.40, 8.01], $t(658) = 10.12, p < .001, d=0.39$. If people had the choice to individually select a vaccine, this would lead to a small average increase in vaccine acceptance by approximately 7%.

[Figure 2 here]

Exploratory Analysis

As first exploratory analysis, we tested several conspiracy belief measures (including government, wellbeing-related, malevolent-global and information-related conspiracy belief (Brotherton et al., 2013)⁴, as the single-item measure (Lantian et al., 2016) and political orientation in one model. We found that wellbeing-related conspiracy beliefs remained the strongest predictor compared to the effects of other, $t(652) = 5.87, p < .001, b = -11.82, 95\% CI$ [-15.78, -7.87], $\beta = -0.31$ (details in Table S2 and Figure 2D). Smaller, but relatively robust effects became apparent by political orientation and the single-item conspiracy measure ($\beta \leq -0.11, ps < .001$).

⁴ The effect of the complete GCBS scale also negatively predicted vaccination acceptance, see supplemental materials, https://osf.io/cqk3n/?view_only=669400c3f57f4a58b3a5c8d74199bea6

Next, as we could confirm the effect of H3 that offering people the choice of vaccines increases their acceptance of the vaccination, we wanted to see for whom this choice matters most. Therefore, we had the choice factor interacting with wellbeing conspiracy beliefs in a 2 (choice: no, yes) \times 3 (conspiracy belief: low tercile, medium tercile and high tercile) mixed ANOVA. We found a main effect for choice ($F(1, 656) = 114.43, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.15$), conspiracy belief ($F(2, 656) = 148.23, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.31$), and the interaction ($F(2, 656) = 10.04, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.03$). This interaction implied that when giving moderate and strong conspiracy believers a choice of the vaccine, this would lead to 10% higher vaccination acceptance, which was not the case for non-believers (see Figure 2C; for simple effects, see Table S2). However, this was probably due to the fact that non-believers already scored very high on the acceptance scale.

Because this effect is potentially of relevance, we conducted an additional study, to confirm this choice effect for strong believers. We could indeed replicate this choice effect: This time, we found the choice main effect ($F(1, 196) = 35.79, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.15$), the conspiracy belief main effect, $F(2, 196) = 24.49, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.20$, and no interaction, $F(2, 196) = 0.06, p = .941, \eta_p^2 = 0.001$. Importantly, strong conspiracy believers (as all the other groups), again indicated to accept the vaccine more, if they could choose it (see also Figure 2C).⁵

Discussion

The present study was conducted during a short time phase, when the Covid vaccination campaign took off in Europe in early 2021. Difficulties in the public communication through political and medical decision makers about how long it would take until the whole population can be provided with a vaccination, complicated by side effects from certain vaccines led to insecurities in parts of the public. In this study, we show how the generic belief in conspiracy theories might have affected the acceptance of a vaccination.

⁵ see supplemental materials for details on the subgroup effects,

https://osf.io/cqk3n?view_only=669400c3f57f4a58b3a5c8d74199bea6

We demonstrated that the media information about the availability of vaccines might not have had an impact on whether people decided to get vaccinated: at least in our experimental manipulation, where we either emphasized that the vaccine will be available to the population soon or that its availability is uncertain (i.e., two messages from the media at the time), did not impact their vaccination decision.

What we found, however, were negative associations of vaccination acceptance with different kinds of conspiracy beliefs, foremost wellbeing-related conspiracy beliefs. These wellbeing-related conspiracy narratives often speak to the concern of believers that big organizations might want to harm them for their purposes, which would explain why the belief in the other conspiracy narratives is not as pronounced: conspiratorial acts by government, economic actors or secret groups are high-level conspiracies, but they may come without a concrete element of direct harm to the people. Hence, these other conspiracies do not connect as well to vaccinations as wellbeing-related conspiracies for believers.

We also found that giving people the choice of a preferred vaccine could slightly increase their vaccination acceptance – an effect that even holds for conspiracy believers, which showed twice. This could be of importance for future vaccination campaigns, where different vaccines are available. We would suggest, however, that this effect should be tested in the field before strong conclusions can be drawn.

As major limitations, four things should be noted. First, our study comprised a convenience sample from mainly social media groups, which had the goal to receive responses from conspiracy believers. Although our sample was relatively large, it cannot be interpreted as a representative sample of the Austrian population at the time.

Second, around half of our sample indicated that they were already registered or received the vaccine. Although without these participants, we could still find similar main effects, this might still have reduced the power of lower order effects.

Three, one could argue that the generic conspiracy scale we used is still too specific with regard to its conspiracy topics (i.e., politics-related, wellbeing-related, small-group related, and

information-related beliefs)⁶. In this regard, it is possible that the use of the generic scale introduced a bias in relation to known Covid-19 conspiracies. Most prominently, the wellbeing-related items contained the component that people are getting harmed, which is also an element of specific Covid-19 and vaccine conspiracies. For instance, conspiracy believers feared that billionaire and vaccine-proponent Bill Gates wanted to implant microchips in humans, or that certain vaccines are not tested long enough so the general public would become pets for the researchers experiments. These specific theories might have been “recognized” in the generic scale items and hence, drew a higher rating on the dependent variables. In the future, one could use an even less topic-specific scale researchers (e.g., Bruder et al., 2013) to circumvent this problem.

Four, with regard to our manipulation material, our short video interventions might have impacted the perception of participants very little compared to the information that was available through the media at the time. As the situation of the early vaccine rollout could be described as a dynamic process where new information was available on a daily basis, it is also highly likely that (most) participants consumed this information. Hence, if this information was salient to them already, it would have been unlikely to cause a difference in the DV to begin with.

⁶ We did not gather data on the “believe in extraterrestrial conspiracies” subscale, as it did not fit topic-wise to the theme of the study and showed poor fit statistics in a replication study (Swami et al., 2014)

References

- Ahmed, W., Vidal-Alaball, J., Downing, J., & Seguí, F. L. (2020). COVID-19 and the 5G conspiracy theory: social network analysis of Twitter data. *Journal of medical internet research*, 22(5), e19458. <https://doi.org/10.2196/19458>
- Brotherton, R., French, C. C., & Pickering, A. D. (2013). Measuring belief in conspiracy theories: The generic conspiracist beliefs scale. *Frontiers in psychology*, 279. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00279>
- Bruder, M., Haffke, P., Neave, N., Nouripanah, N., & Imhoff, R. (2013). Measuring individual differences in generic beliefs in conspiracy theories across cultures: Conspiracy Mentality Questionnaire. *Frontiers in psychology*, 4, 225. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00225>
- Bruns, A., Harrington, S., & Hurcombe, E. (2020). ‘Corona? 5G? or both?’: the dynamics of COVID-19/5G conspiracy theories on Facebook. *Media International Australia*, 177(1), 12-29. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X20946113>
- Callaghan, T., Motta, M., Sylvester, S., Trujillo, K. L., & Blackburn, C. C. (2019). Parent psychology and the decision to delay childhood vaccination. *Social science & medicine*, 238, 112407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2019.112407>
- Douglas, K. M., Sutton, R. M., & Cichocka, A. (2017). The psychology of conspiracy theories. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 26, 538–542. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721417718261>
- European Medicines Agency (2021a). AstraZeneca’s COVID-19 vaccine: EMA finds possible link to very rare cases of unusual blood clots with low blood platelets (April 7, 2021). Retrieved from <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/news/astrazenecas-covid-19-vaccine-ema-finds-possible-link-very-rare-cases-unusual-blood-clots-low-blood>
- European Medicines Agency (2021b). COVID-19 Vaccine AstraZeneca: benefits still outweigh the risks despite possible link to rare blood clots with low blood platelets. European Medicines Agency (March 18, 2021). Retrieved from <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/news/covid-19-vaccine-astrazeneca-benefits-still-outweigh-risks-despite-possible-link-rare-blood-clots>

- Farhart, C. E., Douglas-Durham, E., Trujillo, K. L., & Vitriol, J. A. (2022). Vax attacks: How conspiracy theory belief undermines vaccine support. *Progress in Molecular Biology and Translational Science*, 188(1), 135-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.pmbts.2021.11.001>
- Hviid, A., Hansen, J. V., Frisch, M., & Melbye, M. (2019). Measles, mumps, rubella vaccination and autism: A nationwide cohort study. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 170(8), 513–520. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-2101>
- Infratest Dimap. (2021). ARD-DetschlandTREND April 2021. Retrieved from Infratest Dimap, https://www.infratest-dimap.de/fileadmin/user_upload/DT2104_Bericht.pdf
- Jennings, W., Stoker, G., Bunting, H., Valgarðsson, V. O., Gaskell, J., Devine, D., ... & Mills, M. C. (2021). Lack of trust, conspiracy beliefs, and social media use predict COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy. *Vaccines*, 9(6), 593. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9060593>
- Lantian, A., Muller, D., Nurra, C., & Douglas, K. M. (2016). Measuring belief in conspiracy theories: Validation of a French and English single-item scale. *International Review of Social Psychology*, 29(1), 1-14. <http://doi.org/10.5334/irsp.8>
- Nyhan, B., Dickinson, F., Dudding, S., Dylgjeri, E., Neiley, E., Pullerits, C., ... & Walmsley, C. (2016). Classified or coverup? The effect of redactions on conspiracy theory beliefs. *Journal of Experimental Political Science*, 3(2), 109-123. <https://doi.org/10.1017/XPS.2015.21>
- Oleksy, T., Wnuk, A., Gambin, M., Łyś, A., Bargiel-Matusiewicz, K., & Pisula, E. (2022). Barriers and facilitators of willingness to vaccinate against COVID-19: Role of prosociality, authoritarianism and conspiracy mentality. A four-wave longitudinal study. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 190, 111524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2022.111524>
- Petersen, M. B., Bor, A., Jørgensen, F., & Lindholt, M. F. (2021). Transparent communication about negative features of COVID-19 vaccines decreases acceptance but increases trust. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(29), e2024597118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2024597118>

- Pummerer, L., Winter, K., & Sassenberg, K. (2022). Addressing Covid-19 vaccination conspiracy theories and vaccination intentions. *European Journal of Health Communication, 3*(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.47368/ejhc.2022.201>
- QuestBack GmbH (2021). Unipark Survey Software. Questback GmbH. Available from: <https://www.unipark.com/en/survey-software/>
- Robert Koch Institut. (2021). Pressemitteilung der STIKO zum AstraZeneca-Impfstoff [Press release of the STIKO concerning the AstraZeneca vaccine]. Robert Koch Institut (March 30, 2021). Retrieved from <https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Kommissionen/STIKO/Empfehlungen/AstraZeneca-Impfstoff-2021-03-30.html>
- Rossen, I., Hurlstone, M. J., Dunlop, P. D., & Lawrence, C. (2019). Accepters, fence sitters, or rejecters: Moral profiles of vaccination attitudes. *Social science & medicine, 224*, 23-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2019.01.038>
- Sallam, M., Dababseh, D., Eid, H., Hasan, H., Taim, D., Al-Mahzoum, K., ... & Mahafzah, A. (2021). Low COVID-19 vaccine acceptance is correlated with conspiracy beliefs among university students in Jordan. *International journal of environmental research and public health, 18*(5), 2407. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18052407>
- Salvador Casara, B. G., Suitner, C., & Bettinsoli, M. L. (2019). Viral suspicions: Vaccine hesitancy in the Web 2.0. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied, 25*(3), 354–371. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xap000021>
- Swami, V., Pietschnig, J., Tran, U. S., Nader, I. W., Stieger, S., & Voracek, M. (2013). Lunar lies: The impact of informational framing and individual differences in shaping conspiracist beliefs about the moon landings. *Applied Cognitive Psychology, 27*(1), 71-80. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.2873>
- Swami, V., Barron, D., Weis, L., Voracek, M., Stieger, S., & Furnham, A. (2017). An examination of the factorial and convergent validity of four measures of conspiracist ideation, with recommendations for researchers. *PloS one, 12*(2), e0172617. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0172617>

- Ullah, I., Khan, K. S., Tahir, M. J., Ahmed, A., & Harapan, H. (2021). Myths and conspiracy theories on vaccines and COVID-19: Potential effect on global vaccine refusals. *Vacunas*, 22(2), 93-97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacun.2021.01.001>
- Van Prooijen, J. W., & Douglas, K. M. (2017). Conspiracy theories as part of history: The role of societal crisis situations. *Memory studies*, 10(3), 323-333. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1750698017701615>
- Wood, M. J., Douglas, K. M., & Sutton, R. M. (2012). Dead and alive: Beliefs in contradictory conspiracy theories. *Social psychological and personality science*, 3(6), 767-773. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550611434786>

Figure 1. Timeline with relevant Covid 19 related events in the EU during data collection procedure

Note: EMA = European Medicines Agency, RKI = Robert Koch Institute;

*recommendations from early January by the RKI suggested a vaccination with AstraZeneca for people younger than 65 years of age only, which was changed in mid February; Orlowicz , 2021; European Medical Association, 2021; Robert Koch Institut, 2021

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for all relevant variables for N = 659.

	total		vaccine available		vaccine uncertain		correlations								
	M	(SD)	M	(SD)	M	(SD)	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
1 conspir_govern ($\alpha = .75$)	2.96	(0.96)	2.96	(0.95)	2.96	(0.97)									1
2 conspir_well ($\alpha = .82$)	2.01	(0.99)	1.99	(0.97)	2.03	(1.01)								1	0.57
3 conspir_small ($\alpha = .89$)	2.11	(1.06)	2.08	(1.07)	2.15	(1.06)							1	0.74	0.59
4 conspir_info ($\alpha = .76$)	3.13	(1.05)	3.10	(1.07)	3.17	(1.04)						1	0.59	0.69	0.57
5 conspir_short	4.46	(2.39)	4.50	(2.40)	4.41	(2.38)				1	0.63	0.66	0.69	0.56	
6 political orient.	4.71	(1.72)	4.67	(1.77)	4.75	(1.66)			1	0.32	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.13	
7 DV1 vaccine accept.	72.39	(38.04)	74.24	(37.74)	70.26	(38.35)		1	-0.34	-0.55	-0.49	-0.54	-0.61	-0.36	
8 DV2 vaccine accept.	79.10	(35.11)	80.25	(34.97)	77.77	(35.30)	1	0.9	-0.27	-0.51	-0.45	-0.54	-0.59	-0.36	

Note: vaccine available contain n = 353, vaccine uncertain contain n = 306; polit = political orientation from 1 = very left wing, 6 = center , to 11 = very right wing; GCBS (Brotherton et al., 2013) with Cronbach’s α conspir_govern = government related conspiracies, conspir_well = wellbeing related conspiracies, conspir_small = malevolent global conspiracies, conspir_info = information control conspiracies; conspir_short = single item belief in conspiracy theory scale (Lantian et al., 2016)

Figure 2. Main results of the confirmatory (A, B) and exploratory analysis (C, D).

Note: Panel (A) and (B): means with confidence intervals depict tercile groups (high, medium, low conspiracy belief) confirm the linear model pattern; regression lines are surrounded by 95% confidence shades; panel (C): acceptance means (SE) of high wellbeing conspiracy believers for “no choice” and “choice” in Study 1 and the additional Study 2; panel (D): effect of residual wellbeing conspiracy on residual acceptance score from Table S1 (Supplemental Materials).